

The relationship of midbrain reticular activity with pupil dynamics is modulated by visual contrast

Cyriac, A.¹ and Sieveritz, B.²

¹Neuromatch Academy, Neuromatch, Inc.

²Center for Neural Science, New York University, New York, USA

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Abstract

Neural activity in the midbrain reticular formation (MRF) has been associated with vertical and horizontal saccade control, and with monitoring the eye position during fixation and slow eye movements. Steinmetz et al. (2019) showed two stimuli with varying visual contrasts to mice; one in the left and one in the right hemifield; and simultaneously recorded the neural activity from multiple brain areas. We utilized the dataset and explored whether the relationship of MRF activity with the pupil position or area is modulated by visual input. Our results indicate that it is modulated by the visual contrast of the two presented stimuli, and that the magnitude of modulation is similar for the different measures of pupil dynamics.

Description

Studies in non-human primates have established that multiple brain areas such as the lateral geniculate nucleus (Burr et al., 1994; Büttner et al., 1973; Noda, 1975a; Noda 1975b), the midbrain reticular formation (MRF; Horn, 2006), the superior colliculus (Mohler & Wurtz, 1977; Walker et al., 1995; Wurtz & Mohler, 1976), and the visual cortex (Gilbert & Wiesel, 1983; Livingstone & Hubel, 1984; Tootell et al., 1981) play key roles in gaze and pupil control, and visual processing. The MRF contains neurons with saccade-related activity (Moschovakis et al., 1996; Strassman et al., 1986; Yoshida et al., 1982), neurons that inhibit these saccade neurons during fixation and slow eye movements (Nakao et al., 1989; Nakao et al., 1991; Ohgaki et al.,

1989), and neurons with tonic discharge frequencies that indicate the eye position (Mochovakis et al., 1996). The MRF is connected with other areas involved in gaze control such as the superior colliculus (Edwards & de Olmus, 1976; Moschovakis et al., 1988; Nakao et al., 1990). Neural activity in the superior colliculus is modulated by visual stimuli (Veale & Takahashi, 2024), and neurons in the MRF that receive input from the superior colliculus are active during eye movements (Büttnner et al., 1977; Crawford and Vilis, 1992; Vilis et al., 1989). Furthermore, information about visual stimuli might be relayed to the MRF through the superior vestibular nucleus (Horn, 2006) from visual association cortices (Akbarian et al., 1994). Given the evidence that visual input might modulate MRF activity, we utilized an open-source dataset to investigate whether the relationship between neural activity in the MRF and pupil dynamics is modulated by visual stimuli.

Research Approach

We utilized an open-source dataset from Steinmetz et al. (2019). In each trial, visual stimuli with varying contrast gratings (0%, 25%, 50%, or 100%) were presented on either the left, the right, or both sides of the screen. We focused on trials in which visual stimuli were presented on both sides of the screen. Mice viewed the visual stimulus between 500 and 1200 ms before they turned a wheel to indicate whether the stimulus on the left or right side had the larger visual contrast grating. We focused our data analysis on the first 500 ms of visual stimulus presentation, the minimum length of the stimulus presentation period. Steinmetz et al. (2019) recorded neural activity from various regions in the left hemisphere of the brain in 10 mice across 39 sessions, and tracked the right pupil to record its vertical and horizontal position, and its area. Recordings from the MRF were obtained in 7 mice across 11 sessions, and from a total of 1016 neurons. In

one of the sessions, two visual contrast conditions were missing, and we excluded the 67 neurons that were recorded in that session. Using each possible combination of visual contrasts of stimuli presented on each side of the screen and a time shift of 10 ms, we calculated the cross-correlation between the neural spike train of each MRF neuron and 1) vertical pupil position, 2) horizontal pupil position and 3) pupil area. We then determined the maximum and minimum cross-correlation values across a time shift of 0 to 400 ms, and calculated the mean maximum (MaxCrossCor) and mean minimum (MinCrossCor) cross-correlation values across the recorded MRF neurons.

Results

We first assessed whether the MaxCrossCor and MinCrossCor of MRF activity with vertical pupil position, horizontal pupil position, and pupil area were modulated when the visual contrast monotonically increased across both presented stimuli (left/right = 0%, left/right = 25%, left/right = 50%, and left/right = 100%; **Figure 1A**). **Figure 1B** shows that both the MaxCrossCor and MinCrossCor are modulated by visual contrast. We confirmed that the effect is statistically significant by performing a one-way ANOVA across the four visual contrast levels (mean maximum cross-correlation values - vertical pupil position: $F = 89.6965$, $p < 1e-55$; horizontal pupil position: $F = 57.9321$, $p < 1e-35$; pupil area: $F = 80.4291$, $p < 1e-49$; mean minimum cross-correlation values - vertical pupil position: $F = 71.6253$, $p < 1e-44$; horizontal pupil position: $F = 89.1098$, $p < 1e-54$; pupil area: $F = 69.4178$, $p < 1e-42$). Post hoc tests with a Tukey correction confirmed that the condition where the visual contrast was 0.0 for both the left and right presented stimulus was significantly different from any of the other three conditions for any of the examined relationships between MRF activity and pupil dynamics.

Figure 1. Maximum and minimum cross-correlation coefficients. **A-** Average MRF activity across neurons, and average pupil area, horizontal pupil position, and vertical pupil position across sessions when gratings with the same visual contrast were presented on both sides of the screen, and **C-** when both the left and right visual stimulus had either low (0% and 25%) or high (50% and 100%) visual contrast. **B- and D-** The mean +/- the standard error of the maximum and minimum cross-correlation coefficients of MRF activity with different pupil dynamics for the same conditions shown in A and C, respectively.

We further assessed whether interaction of the right and left visual contrast correlated with the magnitude of modulation. We aggregated the data across low (0%, and 25%) and high (50%, and 100%) visual contrast conditions. **Figure 1C** shows the average MRF activity and pupil measurements across the resulting combinations of conditions. **Figure 1D** shows that both MaxCrossCor and MinCrossCor values are smallest when the visual contrast of the stimulus presented on the right side is low while the left visual contrast is high. MaxCrossCor and MinCrossCor values are slightly more positive / negative when the visual contrast of the stimulus presented on the left side is low, independent of the visual contrast of the right side visual stimulus, and are largest when both of the presented visual stimuli have high visual contrast. We examined whether these qualitative differences were statistically significant by performing a two-way ANOVA using both the left and right visual contrast as a two-level factor. The main effect of left visual contrast, and the interaction effect of left and right visual contrast were significant for both the MaxCrossCorr and MinCrossCor values across any of the examined relationships between MRF activity and pupil dynamics ($F > 27$; $p < 1e-6$).

Given that MRF firing patterns are known to differ during saccades and when the animal fixates or makes slow eye movements, we excluded data from times during which the animals made a saccade and repeated the analyses (see **Supplementary Material**). These analyses had similar results, strongly indicating that the modulation of the relationship between MRF activity and pupil dynamics by visual contrast is not an artifact due to different ratios of saccade to fixation MRF activity in different visual contrast conditions.

Discussion

We showed that the relationship of MRF activity with three different measurements of pupil dynamics; the vertical and horizontal eye position, and the pupil area; is modulated by visual contrast. The magnitude of the modulation systematically varies based on the visual contrast of the stimuli presented in the ipsi- and contralateral hemifield, and is similar across the three measurements of pupil dynamics. As expected, modulation was largest when both the left and right stimulus contrast were high. However, modulation was not smallest when both stimuli contrasts were low. Instead, it was smallest when the right stimulus contrast was low as the left stimulus contrast remained high. These results indicate that modulation is mainly driven by the visual contrast of the right stimulus. Given that MRF activity was recorded from the left hemisphere, the result is not surprising as visual information presented on the right side of the screen and entering through the right eye is processed in the left hemisphere, which results in a larger dependence of neural activity in the left side of the brain on visual stimuli presented in the right hemifield.

A limitation of our result is that previous work which showed that MRF activity relates to horizontal and vertical saccades, and eye position during fixation and slow eye movements was performed in non-human primates and cats. We made the implicit assumption that these findings translate to mice, but anatomical differences might limit cross-species translatability. However, a recent review (Giovannetti & Rancz, 2024) highlighted that at least some gaze control mechanisms translate between non-human primates and mice. Overall, our findings extend on previous work and indicate that the relationship of MRF activity with pupil dynamics is modulated by visual inputs.

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